

CURRENT PROBLEM OF OBESITY

Rasulova N. F.

Sattarova Z. R.

Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute, Uzbekistan

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10550942>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 15th January 2024

Accepted: 21th January 2024

Online: 22th January 2024

KEY WORDS

ABSTRACT

Relevance. In recent years, it is rare to find a person who has not access heard about the "Problem of the 21st century" – obesity, do not have access to TV or information .The World Health Organization WHO estimates that obesity has become an epidemic worldwide [1]: with at least 2.8 million people dying each year as a result of being overweight or obese. Currently, obesity, previously associated with high-income countries, is also common in low-and middle-income countries. Being overweight and obese are major risk factors for a range of diseases, including diabetes, heart disease, and cancer. The problem of overweight and obesity, once considered specific to high-income countries, is now becoming widespread in low-and middle-income countries, especially in urban settings. The following are some recent WHO global estimates [2]: In 2019, more than 1.9 billion adults over the age of 18 were overweight. Of these, over 650 million were obese. According to data from 2019 , 39% of adults over the age of 18 (39% of men and 40% of women) were overweight. In 2021, about 13% of the world's adult population (11% of men and 15% of women) were obese. From 1985 to 2019, the number of obese people worldwide more than tripled. An estimated 41 million children under the age of 5 were overweight or obese in 2019. The United States leads the world in terms of the number of people who are obese. 38.2% of Americans over the age of 15 are overweight [5], and in 2030 this figure may exceed 45%. In second place is Mexico, where 32.4% of the population is overweight. In third place is New Zealand, where 30.7% of people are diagnosed with obesity. The least overweight population is in Japan, where only 3.7% of the population is obese. Russia is located in the middle of the rating: 19.6% of Russians are overweight [5]. By definition, obesity is the deposition of fat, an increase in body weight due to adipose tissue[3,4]. Simple fats are compounds of the triatomic alcohol glycerol with three fatty acids and include only three chemical elements-carbon, hydrogen and oxygen. A person can synthesize fat from carbohydrates. Fats found in the body of different animals differ in the length of fatty acid chains and the presence of double bonds in them. The smaller the double bonds, the denser the fatty acid molecules adhere to each other, and the fat is harder. Vegetable fats remain liquid even in

the refrigerator. The body is able to build up and shorten chains, and therefore can be satisfied with any fat. But still, the consumption of animal fats, including butter, is mandatory for humans - only they contain vitamins A and D (carrots and yeast contain their predecessors - carotene and ergosterol). Vegetable fats contain essential polyunsaturated fatty acids- linoleic acid and linolenic acid. They are so important for the body that they are considered vitamins (vitamin F). In addition, vegetable oils are a source of vitamin E, which in animal products is found only in the liver. The main cause of obesity and overweight is an energy imbalance, in which the caloric content of the diet exceeds the energy needs of the body [1]. The following trends are being observed around the world: increased consumption of high-energy-density and high-fat foods; reduced physical activity due to the increasingly sedentary nature of many activities, changes in modes of movement, and increasing urbanization. For the diagnosis of overweight and obesity, the "Body Mass Index" (BMI) is used. You can determine the body mass index by the formula : $BMI = \text{weight (kg)} / \text{height (m}^2\text{)}$. Interpretation of BMI indicators, in accordance with the recommendations of the World Health Organization (WHO):

16 or less - weight deficit.

16-18.5 - insufficient (deficit) body weight;

18.5-25 - the norm.

25-30 - overweight (pre-obesity).

30-35 - first-degree obesity.

30-35 - first-degree obesity.

35-40 - second-degree obesity.

40 or more - third-degree obesity (morbid).

An increased BMI is one of the main risk factors for such diseases.

non-communicable diseases, such as:

- cardiovascular diseases (mainly heart disease and stroke), which were the leading cause of death in 2012;
- diabetes;
- disorders of the musculoskeletal system (especially osteoarthritis
- extremely disabling degenerative joint disease);
- certain cancers (including endometrial, breast, ovarian, prostate, liver, gallbladder, kidney, and colon cancers). Childhood obesity increases the likelihood of obesity, premature death, and disability in adulthood. In addition to the increased risk in the future, obese children also experience shortness of breath, are at an increased risk of fractures, are prone to hypertension, early signs of cardiovascular disease, insulin resistance, and may experience psychological problems [6]. Among the strategies developed to combat obesity, the best results are:
- increase in prices for potentially harmful products;
- communication policy aimed at combating obesity;
- information displayed on food labels;
- as well as the use of social networks and mass media to inform the public about the dangers of excess weight. There is also such a term as orthorexia nervosa (eating disorder), characterized by an obsessive desire for "healthy and proper nutrition", which leads to significant restrictions in the choice of food. It is believed that orthorexia is a type of obsessive-compulsive disorder and hypochondria [7]. For the study, we decided to choose the problem

of obesity among students of school No. 274 in Tashkent. A representative sample included 42 people from grades 8 and 9 (15 and 16 years of age). Respondents were asked to answer two questions anonymously:

Do you know how to detect obesity?

Are you obese?

They can detect obesity 15 18

They don't know how to detect obesity 8 2

They are diagnosed with obesity 5 1

Based on the impersonal results obtained from the school's medical room, it was found that in grades 1-11 of School No. 274, only 7 people suffer from obesity. There are no children with diagnosed obesity in the sample of students in grades 8-9. Therefore, we can conclude that the problems associated with excess body weight are very acutely perceived by girls at the age of early adolescence. It is during this period that girls are prone to an eating disorder (anorexia) [7]. From the analysis of tabular data, it can be concluded that young men and women are aware of the problems of obesity. But this is just a misinterpretation of the results, and is a personal opinion of the survey participants. When talking to students, it was found that only 30% know about BMI and how to calculate it. 70% of children identify obesity visually, which in 100% does not coincide with the actual result, but is only a reflection of their worldview. It should be noted that students in grades 8-9 have ideas about a healthy lifestyle, but they are not whole or distorted. Students' parents and school teachers serve as sources of information about healthy lifestyles. Often, parents misunderstand the criteria and concepts of healthy lifestyle. The information available on the Internet does not always reflect the current views of medical science in the field of healthy lifestyle and obesity. But often information about healthy lifestyle is not interesting for young men and women. Many people do not see problems in obesity apart from aesthetic ones. To increase the share of children who are responsible for their own health, I consider it necessary to promote knowledge related to the field of healthy lifestyle.

References:

1. WHO Newsletter. Obesity and overweight. <https://www.who.int/ru/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/obesity-and-overweight>
2. WHO. Health issues. Fatness. <https://www.who.int/topics/obesity/ru/>
3. Obesity. Material from Wikipedia. <https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/Fatness>
4. Prozorovsky V. Obezhirenie – bolezne nashego vremeni [Obesity as a disease of our time]. Doctor of Medical Sciences. Article in the journal "Science and life" <https://www.nkj.ru/archive/articles/3380/>
5. News publishing house. <https://ria.ru/20170522/1494835889.html>
6. Childhood obesity. about risk factors. Translation of the article. http://medspecial.ru/for_doctors/29/24604/
7. Eating disorders. Material from Wikipedia. https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/Food_Intake_Upsets#Nerve_anorexia